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Digital platform and analytic tools for energy

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Terms and Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
LI	LinkedIn
OC	Open Call
PU	Public
TTP	Technology Transfer Programme
TW	Twitter
WP	Work Package
YT	YouTube

Executive Summary

This deliverable is framed in task 7.3. Community Portal, reinforcing activities of the Work Package 7, “WP7-Open Call Management and Ecosystem Building”. The communication insight behind is how we can *“create something tangible and dynamic as a lively and active community of relevant stakeholders”*. This is why the PLATOON Community is the online arena where members can have a dialogue with other peers, sharing knowledge and expertise in one digital platform.

1 Introduction

The document describes the relevance of **PLATOON Online Community** in the project, as well as its purpose and a wide variety of functionalities, that invite users to participate, share content and find new ways to interact with each other.

The members of this community will be players and amplifiers of the project (described in Section 3.1), along with the voice of supportive partners and ambassadors.

1.1 Intended audience of the document

Even if this is a public document, it is intended to be used internally by Consortium partners to let them know how we are planning and executing to build a community and frame PLATOON into its ecosystem.

2. Alignment with the communication plan

This deliverable, as well as the Community building task itself, are closely linked to Task 9.1. Dissemination and Communication Strategy plan and Task 9.4: Communication and General Dissemination, and should be aligned with objectives, audiences and directives described on them and leverage on the activities, materials and communication channels described in this document.

2. 1. Objectives

As outlined in the proposal, the purpose of the Community Portal is to transform the traditional static dissemination and communication actions of a project into **something more dynamic and alive**, capable to engage with relevant stakeholders around the PLATOON facilitating knowledge exchange and peer-to-peer learning among all players and amplifying their outreach activities.

In this regard, this task plays a major role in contributing to the dissemination of the PLATOON message. In fact, the goal of the PLATOON Community is to create a rich ecosystem of active members interacting, finding synergies and getting value from the different stakeholders of the project.

Content in the community should be appealing to attract and engage involved members in the ecosystem, offering them a clear understanding of digitisation of the energy sector and all the benefits it can bring from a technological, economical and societal point of view. But, most important, giving them an opportunity to contribute with their own insights and experience. The sharing of this knowledge will both help enrich the PLATOON approach and impact and the better fitting of members' perspective, needs and requirements.

On the **dissemination** side, those objectives to which the community can contribute most are:

- To timely **disseminate technological knowledge** generated in the project within and beyond the project duration.
- To **establish liaisons** with other projects and initiatives for knowledge and innovation transfer.
- To **engage the targeted audiences** to get feedback and validate the project's results.

The community, which will be the main place to disseminate the documents collecting the knowledge and the information about the technology produced during PLATOON execution, is the best place to communicate about the benefits of applying PLATOON outcomes, by leveraging onto use case experiences, and to build on PLATOON outcomes.

In this particular case, interaction in the community among those partners participating in PLATOON use cases and the potential adopters invited to private spaces in the community will make a substantial difference.

3. PLATOON Community

PLATOON COMMUNITY, was built using the FundingBox community platform¹. This is a **dynamic and interactive** web-based platform that includes communication services fostering collaborative work, aiming at facilitating interaction among stakeholders and providing information on best practices,

¹ <https://spaces.fundingbox.com/c/platoon>

trends in the market, etc. The FundingBox platform largely evolved over the time, thanks to users' feedback and new features have been implemented in order to offer an ideal tool to **build up communities around projects and initiatives**.

The PLATOON project consortium designed the PLATOON COMMUNITY with an inclusive perspective promoting the inclusion not only of the PLATOON related activities and results but acting also as a gathering **for all those stakeholders interested in the digitisation of the energy sector**. Therefore, the PLATOON community has a wider ambition and perspective than just being the community of the PLATOON project, aiming to become the community of reference in Europe for anyone working or wanting to know more information about the digitisation of the energy sector.

PLATOON Community is benefitting from the FundingBox experience in building communities for several other European projects such as the [I-ENERGY²](#), [I4MS³](#), [INTERCONNECT⁴](#) community and more, with the objective of **transforming** what usually are **static unidirectional websites in a dynamic multidirectional community**, where connections are made and where conversations and knowledge can be gathered and shared.

This communication channel aims to create a real-time community where its participants will be able to easily access a repository of knowledge and finding long-term business opportunities.

3.1. Target audience

Our target audience for PLATOON has already been detailed in Deliverable 9.3 (Communication and Dissemination Report). The stakeholder groups below are all potential users of the PLATOON Community.

STAKEHOLDER GROUP	BRIEF DESCRIPTION	WHY IS PLATOON INTERESTING TO THEM?
PLATOON Consortium partners	All 20 partners directly involved in the PLATOON project. Wide range of institutions: enterprises, research institutes, public institutions, etc.	PLATOON is of crucial importance to all Consortium partners as it aligns fully with their organisational goals and strategic direction in the domains of digitalisation and the energy sector in particular

²I-ENERGY aims at evolving, scaling up and demonstrating innovative AI-as-a-Service (AIaaS) Energy Analytics Applications and digital twins services that will be validated along 9 pilots: <https://spaces.fundingbox.com/c/i-ENERGY>

³ ICT Innovation for Manufacturing SMEs (I4MS) promoted by the European Commission to expand the digital innovation of manufacturing SMEs in Europe: <https://spaces.fundingbox.com/c/i4ms>

⁴ INTERCONNECT aims to to develop and demonstrate advanced solutions for connecting and converging digital homes and buildings with the electricity sector in 7 connected large-scale test sites

<p>Energy generation companies/ Energy Service Companies (ESCOs)/ Renewable Energy (REN) Companies</p>	<p>Commercial enterprises that focus on generating electricity, heat, hot water etc., as well as energy services to businesses and private households. Also focus on companies that specialize in renewable energy, green electricity trading and e-mobility.</p>	<p>Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data.</p> <p>Operation and maintenance of REN power plants, as well as electricity grids can be improved (f.e. easier to foresee upcoming maintenance work, optimised grids thus longer lifespan of those).</p> <p>The project aims to increase the RE share within the energy sector. By doing so, new REN businesses could be created which is especially good for start-ups and companies with innovative business models.</p>
<p>TSOs/ DSOs</p>	<p>Transmission System Operators and Distribution System Operators that operate and maintain electricity and gas grids; those who provide whole local areas or municipalities with energy.</p>	<p>Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data.</p>
<p>Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) specialised in the Energy sector (i.e. providers) or interested in applying the</p>	<p>Small and medium-sized companies that focus on a business that is very closely linked to the energy sector; f.e. energy-heavy industries such as the automotive sector, mechanical engineering sector, pharma sector, construction sector etc.</p>	<p>Should be prepared for emerging big data in the energy sector; links to partners with expertise in Big Data.</p> <p>The project aims to increase the REN share within the energy sector. By doing so, new REN businesses could be created, and this could be a chance for industries that could provide these with services, goods, know-how etc.</p>

results (i.e. adopters).	Especially those companies that have innovative and future-oriented business models.	
Universities and Research centres	Public and private research and educational institutions that focus on providing people with constantly improving and up-to-date knowledge.	The project results/ milestone results are an important input that could enable universities and research centres to exchange knowledge, technology, data etc. and provide other stakeholders with valuable information (f.e. other scientific institutes, companies, etc.).
Funding agencies	Commercial enterprises and public institutions (f.e. Economic development companies) that are providing start-ups, SMEs and projects on EU level with know-how and financial resources.	Funding agencies focus on state-of-the-art developments in their sector. PLATOON being an innovative project funded by the EC, will make sure to communicate its output to funding agencies in relevant domains.
Technological Platforms & Professional Associations and Initiatives	Public platforms that focus on technology-based topics such as Big Data, data Science etc. Example: Leibniz-Gemeinschaft.	PLATOON implements the digitalisation of the energy sector. Its use cases and pilots are highly relevant to related platforms and associations in terms of technology transfer, state of the art and lessons learned which can spur further synergies.

Table 1: PLATOON Community Target Audience.

3.2 Introduction: Features of the Community Platform

FundingBox communities offers **information** (trends, news, events, technology news, funding opportunities), **inspiration** (exclusive content curated by experts and interlocutors: live chats, Q&As...), **support** (experts will advise, but members can also create synergies and build partnerships) and **connections** (by networking with people interested in the digitisation of the energy sector domain).

3.2.1. Overall description of Community Platform

FundingBox Platform is mostly a communication tool where knowledge is shared for the sake of the community, with two main features.

- Its main characteristic is a chat base mode (Spaces) that serves as a base to communicate and interact among the parties (1 to many users or 1:1).
- This is complemented by what we call Collections; content repositories that empower users to build and share knowledge.

3.2.2. Main features

- **Spaces:** Each community is formed by “Spaces”; each Space is a channel of communication. They can be defined and shaped according to the needs of each community. Main features in FundingBox communities are created under “**Spaces**”. A “**Space**” is a section where information related to a specific topic is posted. Each community identifies, decides and creates the “**Spaces**” that address its needs.

Figure 1: FundingBox platform, example of space at the PLATOON community.

- **Collections:** Collections include a set of features to empower crowd knowledge creation and interaction among users within a space. Basically, a collection allows users to publish specific contents in spaces (collection content is announced to the community in one specific channel

/ space) and gather together in one single place all those publications with a specific aim (i.e. articles, events, questions, etc...).

In the case of PLATOON, we have so far created tailor made collections that focus on the items shown in Figure 2 below.

Collections

Explore our content by choosing a specific collection below.

Figure 2: Collections within the PLATOON Community

The different features in Collections can be activated or hidden according to the needs of each community, and may include:

I Active features:

- **Articles** - Each community can publish articles related to their interests. It can be blog posts, articles related to the topic of interest, etc
- **Announcements/News** - Members of the communities have the option to post announcements, questions and events. This increases the interactions within members of the community, creates connections and enhances the relations among them.
- **Events**, where one can create a specific events repository for each community, allowing the users to share forthcoming events within a concrete community related topic.
- **Questions** - an FAQ section about specific subtopics within the community community members can post questions. Questions can be answered by any member and the results can be voted.
- Supportive Partners section that includes information about our Supportive Partners (see 4.1).
- Explore other Communities section, where users can get familiar with other communities and interact with them.

II Features to be activated:

- **Ideas**, where members can post ideas on different topics related to the community and get feedback from other members, including experts.
- **Discussions and Stories**, where members can share insights focused on a single discussion topic or share stories of interest.
- **Marketplaces / Showcases**, where each community can decide to have one or more marketplaces to showcase specific companies, products, professionals, services etc. This feature will be activated, once the 1st Technology Transfer Programme kicks off.

We will take advantage of the above-mentioned features taking into account the communication and dissemination strategy, as well as the timeline of the project. For instance, the feature "Marketplaces

/ Showcases" will be activated when the 1st Technology Transfer Programme (TTP) has kicked off. This way, the selected beneficiaries will be able to showcase their company, or PoC/MVP, once developed. Features "Idea" and "Discussions and Stories" will be activated during the 1st TTE as well in order to trigger fruitful discussions among the beneficiaries/mentors/pilots, and exchange ideas.

Figure 3: Announcements Collection within the PLATOON Community

3.2.3. Advantages of FundingBox Platform

There are several software solutions, however, none of them are able to cover all the functionalities offered by the FundingBox solution. FundingBox solution offers the **administrator the possibility to customise the community by adding the desired features** and putting the emphasis in the **crowd knowledge base approach**.

In the following we list a set of key benefits that PLATOON is leveraging thanks to the adoption of the FundingBox platform.

- **Mobile apps**

Mobile access is crucial to build communities. For this reason, FundingBox has developed mobile apps available in the App Store and Google Play Store. This gives a lot of immediacy to users to be able to post and hold conversations. A desktop app will be released in the coming months.

- **A community of over 37.000 makers, entrepreneurs, startups and tech SMEs**

FundingBox gathers over 37.000 makers and entrepreneurs that are part of several of the communities built in FundingBox. Among the +37.000 registered members there are several communities with content associated with the PLATOON community, some of these are the ones associated with Industry 4.0, smart manufacturing, Start-ups' Acceleration, Decentralized Technologies, Digital Innovation Hubs, GDPR, among others. These areas, related to internet developments, will help to cross disseminate information and create a certain awareness about the PLATOON community.

- **Capacity to evolve the platform**

Being a platform built by FundingBox, we are all ears to evolve the platform according to the inputs and requests of the FundingBox and PLATOON community. This gives us flexibility to include certain features and requests in the platform roadmap development.

3.3. PLATOON Community Spaces and Collections

Taking into account the success of other communities, such as I4MS, which counts close to 1.500 users, we are exploring new possibilities to find connections between different initiatives such as I-ENERGY and others. That is, merging communities in order to increase the visibility of PLATOON, to have a bigger impact on its audience. For instance, I-ENERGY is a Community about AI for Next Generation Energy, powered by FundingBox. It has been approved under ICT-49 (AI4EU initiative) and funded under GA no 101016508. This community is already showcasing PLATOON on the [Explore Other Communities collection](#).

With that purpose the community will be open to any user interested in the topic with no need to sign up to see and access the content. Once the user wants to interact somehow with the community either posting any content, joining the conversation or wanting to connect with anyone, the sign up will be required.

3.3.1. Design of the community

Public spaces will be open to anybody visiting the community. Their purpose is providing general information about PLATOON and the domain it addresses and, specially, facilitate interaction, connections and knowledge sharing of members.

The following public Spaces are currently operating:

- **PLATOON News, events articles and more.** The place to post content, as per example news, articles or reports about the pilots and deployments in the facilities of the big industry partners involved, as well as other activities that might occur during the project.
- **PLATOON Questions and Answers.** The public questions and answer channel to communicate with Open Call applicants to solve their doubts (dedicated support channel) or to guide them in the community.

Figure 4: FundingBox platform, the landing page of the PLATOON project community

3.3.2. Type of content

Partners of the project will act as the first community curators, so the first collections of content will be provided by FBA, who will produce content about the services provided by PLATOON, different kinds of technologies, use cases, best practices, technical services, funding opportunities, events, meetups and interesting news.

The content shared in the community will be the following:

- News and articles interesting about the energy sector and its digitisation.
- PLATOON Open Calls and other Funding opportunities information
- Multimedia content such as images, videos and infographics.
- Events organized, but also other relevant events at European level attended by the partners of the project.
- Other communities information and access
- Info about Supportive partners of the project
- Best practices and success stories to inspire innovative SMEs, organizations and researchers to build those solutions around the digitisation of the energy sector.
- Q&A sessions with experts who can share their knowledge and expertise with the community members.

Figure 5: Community settings screen at the PLATOON Community.

3.4. PLATOON Community Access

The PLATOON Community is highly exposed in the project website which is the door of entrance to the PLATOON initiative. To achieve that aim, a remarkable “Join PLATOON Community” button, banner, etc... will be added to the portal, linking to the specific PLATOON Community portal access that should have an URL under the PLATOON domain.

The community is open with no need to register to access the main content of the community. The idea is that people can easily access the main content and if they want to participate, they need to login to the platform.

4. Community Entry Points

The ecosystem – broadly understood, i.e. the set of all stakeholders around the PLATOON project are being reached through all communication channels and partners’ networks and invited to join the PLATOON Online Community, as a place for exchange and interaction, through any of those entry points.

This will systematically be done through the stakeholder mapping and following the liaising strategy and through targeted communication actions at the different entry points, as stated in the following paragraphs.

4.1. Supportive Partners & Ambassadors

The Supportive Partners Programme for communities involves entities from across Europe, such as

start-up communities, accelerators, governments, programmes and more to help PLATOON to empower innovation and entrepreneurship in the crossroads of ICT and energy and connect the ecosystem. The “supportive partners” are stakeholders interested in disseminating the project in a win-win cooperation mode. These are identified via community mapping, starting from the PLATOON partners’ networks. To date we have 15 supportive partners who have expressed interest in entering a co-branding relationship with PLATOON. Cooperation with 8 of these companies has started, see the list of these companies below. Collaboration with the 7 other companies is planned to kick-start in the coming month.

List of 8 supportive partners with whom the collaboration has kick-started:

- BDVA
- BerriUp
- EIT Inno Energy
- SZ REDA
- Tenerrdis
- Vestbee
- WeSmart
- Reengen

Ambassadors, on the other hand, are experts, with a clear reputation, strong connections with companies, universities, governments and the start-up ecosystem in Europe and with a proven previous experience in big data and energy sectors. The Ambassador programme will be paramount to shape and give live to the PLATOON community. This programme will be key to create a crowd knowledge base repository and a thrilling and active community.

To date, three ambassadors have been selected to represent PLATOON. These are responsible for participating in the dissemination activities, from publishing in the Community, creating best practices and participating in Q&A and/or webinars. The criteria for ambassador selection is their background, strong existing network and relevance to the PLATOON project (e.g. experience in big data). The Ambassadors selected for this project meet the criteria, and are presented below:

1. [Nathalie Mitton](#), Inria
2. [Jad Nassar](#), Yncréa
3. [Thorsten Huelmann](#), International Data Spaces

4.2. Promotional activities within PLATOON Community

People contribute to online communities to share information, network, research, and learn. Most people are members of a community because they’re passionate about certain topics.

Promoting the PLATOON project within the community will certainly increase awareness and build excitement around it. Community marketing is a strategy that involves forming an engaging brand (project) presence in order to interact with a community of existing members and by doing so, finally bring more members to it.

We are actively creating an online presence pointing to the community, throughout the official project website and social media accounts, during the whole project cycle.

Leverage community online events

While the ultimate goal of the community event may be to attract new members, it's also an opportunity to connect again with current members. We will reach out to current members - via email, community spaces announcements, social media, to let them know about the certain online event we are holding or streaming. Using existing channels and member's touchpoints is one of the best ways to promote it. We will also (when possible) ask project partners to share the event news throughout their relevant networks.

The FundingBox Platform has the capabilities of organising online initiatives such as the following:

- **Webinars** - an engaging online event where a speaker, or small group of speakers, deliver a presentation to a large audience who participate by submitting questions, responding to polls and using other available interactive tools.
- **Online group discussions** - refers to an online communicative situation that allows its participants to share their views and opinions with other participants. It is a systematic exchange of information, views and opinions about a topic, problem, issue or situation among the members of a group who share some common objectives. 4 group chat related to the use cases will be created to promote lively conversations regarding the specific use cases
- **Webcasts** - media presentation distributed over the Internet using streaming media technology to distribute a single content source to many simultaneous listeners/viewers – “broadcasting”
- **Live chat activities:** FundingBox Platform is making it possible to hold live chats inside the community. This means that all members can easily connect with each other, for networking, sharing knowledge and interest, solving doubts and problems.
- **Micro-polls and surveys:** A well-designed survey can be a key component in the members retention program. By asking questions that quiz the audience on areas such as support and information, we can find out what it takes to keep them (members around). The idea is to possibly organize a micro poll or a survey right after holding the event inside the community in order to have them give us feedback without interruption, and in turn, giving us the opportunity to meet their satisfaction by following up on that same feedback they gave us.
- **PLATOON supportive communities:** FundingBox Platform has very well established project communities (I4MS, DIHNET, Ledger, etc.), which provide the possibility to make a community cross-dissemination of any kind of content.
- **Success stories or use cases presentation:** We will be actively sharing outcomes of PLATOON tasks inside the community (documents related to the state-of-the-art, requirements, specifications, standardization, etc.).
- **Activities of support:** The community will also be used as one type of a technical help desk, to help people of interest with possible technical issues i.e. details about the project, help on how to use the community platform or technical support around implementing business cases.

4.3. Portal website

The PLATOON website is managed by Partner TIB (responsible for WP9). The website is the main entry door targeting the general public, with the aim of raising awareness and explaining the PLATOON ambition and value proposition. The website provides basic information about the project and sets several points of access to the community.

Interested people can learn about the project in the site, but the main objective is attracting those target audiences, involved in the digitisation of the energy sector, to on-board as members to PLATOON Online Community, which is more of a dynamic platform compared to the website (that will

be more static regarding the content) where they can interact with consortium partners and other actors in the ecosystem, contribute with their insights or just stay updated on the status of PLATOON use cases or trends in this domain.

The button to join the PLATOON community will always be at reach and especially visible on the website.

Figure 6: Portal website.

When decided, the above-mentioned community activities will be announced on the website so all content published on the website will redirect the visitor to the relevant community links/spaces.

4.4. Social media and networking strategy

Another key entry point for PLATOON to increase the visibility of PLATOON COMMUNITY will be social media networks. Thus, to grow the PLATOON network and to convince stakeholders to join, an active promotion of the community via the already available PLATOON initiative social media channels will be made, namely, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube.

The messages spread in these social media accounts will be news, milestones and activities about the project that are relevant, interactive and engaging. Social media will be key to generate awareness about PLATOON as a European initiative and as a community. This action will be aligned with the overall communication strategy developed in task 9.1. “Communication and Dissemination Plan”.

4.5. Other actions

a) Partners networks.

In order to leverage on the partners' network, we are coordinating actions with the partners to promote the community and the relevant different pieces of content generated. The idea is to include always a link to the community where the pieces of content are placed. This way we expect to attract and bring more users to the community leveraging on the social media and other dissemination channels of the partners.

Similarly, when a key piece of content is generated, we will push using the partners' networks to get them published in other media and addressing specific influencers in twitter through triggers and calls to action; or promoting catchy offerings through social media channels for early adopters.

b) Newsletter and newsflashes

Relevant pieces of PLATOON content and PRs will be, when decided and possible, included in the newsletters that will be laid out in the communication plan, task. 9.1., (and optionally, the newsletters from other PLATOON consortium partners) aiming to drive people to join and explore the PLATOON community.

c) Off-line events

Regarding the offline events, we will always try to take some dissemination promotional materials (flyers and brochures, visit cards to join the community action) when being present at the event.

Moreover, we will do our best to always showcase the access to the PLATOON community.

We will also use the possibility to follow up on an event discussion in the community, after and during the event.

4.6. Analytics

We follow up the impact of communication actions in community building, to watch for the project to reach its Key Performance Indicators in terms of dissemination and also to search for potential improvements and implement corrective actions if needed. Our target is to reach 250 members.

We measure the following metrics using platform analytics tools that will contribute to measure the attractiveness and dynamics of the community platform:

- Number of users (sign-ups, new members)
- Numbers of messages (content) posted in the certain period (posts, announcements, files, articles)
- Number of reactions to the content in the certain period
- Number of comments to the content in the certain period
- Other engagement metrics of the community, like percentage of visits during the last 30 days.

Members	114
Interacting users	135
Messages	82

Replies/Comments	49
Reactions	38

Table 2: PLATOON Community in numbers updated to June 01, 2021.

Based on the Figure below, there appears to have been a surge during the Open Call launch in January, which closed at the beginning of March 2021.

Key Charts

Figure 6: Chart with the new signups in the community.

5. Conclusion

The Community Portal is a living tool that will grow together with the wider PLATOON ecosystem that is nourished by a number of avenues ranging from partners’ networks, to PLATOON Supportive Partners and Ambassadors. We aim to reach our KPI by using both a proactive outreach to relevant organisations as well as the snowballing effect that will broaden the ecosystem through networks of networks.

For the remaining project time June 2021 to December 2022, we aim to progressively grow our community by:

- creating public awareness on the Open Call finalists
- creating a forum for the finalists to discuss their views on big data and energy
- creating a marketplace for finalists to publicise about their solutions
- using our Ambassadors and Supportive Partners to draw their communities to the portal
- using our Project Partners to encourage their networks to engage with the PLATOON community
- creating Call To Actions via social media and other platforms to encourage newcomers to join the portal

Currently, the engagement rate of the community is 0,37%, which is considered as high value (using Twitter as a benchmark). The set KPIs by the end of the project are presented in the table below.

Members	250
Interacting users	250
Messages	150
Replies/Comments	70
Reactions	80

Table 3: PLATOON Community KPIs by the end of the project.

We hope to grow the community to have a lasting impact on the energy domain, as well as continue to inform interested parties on other avenues of funding or communities for them to grow their networks and revenue.

5.1 Internal Review 1

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes	N= no	NA = not applicable
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Name of reviewer: Jiménez Segado, Eduardo

Organisation: Minsait

Date: June 10, 2021

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
FORMAT: Does the document ...?					
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?	Y				
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?		N			
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?	Y				
... contain a version table?	Y				
... contain an updated table of contents?	Y				
... contain a list of figures?	Y				
... contain a list of tables?	Y				
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	Y			It'S necessary to review (some of them missing)	
... contain an Executive Summary?	Y				
... contain a Conclusions section?	Y				
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?	Y				
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?	Y				
... use correct spelling and grammar?	Y				
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)	Y				
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)			NA		

... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy & paste text)	Y				
About the content...					
Is the deliverable content correctly written?	Y				
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?	Y				
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?	Y				
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?	Y				
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?	Y				
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?		N			
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?		N			
Are all references in the document included in the references section?	Y				
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)		N			
TECHNICAL RESEARCH WPs (WP2-WP5)					
Is the deliverable sufficiently innovative?					
Does the document present technical soundness and its methods are correctly explained?					
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?					
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?					
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.					

VALIDATION WP (WP6)				
Does the document present technical soundness and the validation methods are correctly explained?				
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?				
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?				
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.				
DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION WPs (WP8 & WP9)				
Does the document present a consistent outreach and exploitation strategy?				
Are the methods and means correctly explained?				
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?				
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?				
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.				

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

	Document accepted; no changes required.
X	Document accepted; changes required.
	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5.

(1-Poor; 2-Fair; 3-Average; 4-Good; 5-Excellent)

Using a half point scale.

Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5
							X		

5.2 Internal Review 2

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes	N= no	NA = not applicable
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Name of reviewer: Jose I. Hormaeche

Organisation: Cluster de Energía (CEPV)

Date: 11/06/2021

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	Comments	Author
FORMAT: Does the document ...?					
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?	Y				
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?	Y				
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?	Y				
... contain a version table?	Y				
... contain an updated table of contents?	Y				
... contain a list of figures?	Y				
... contain a list of tables?	Y				
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?	Y				
... contain an Executive Summary?	Y				
... contain a Conclusions section?	Y				
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?	Y				
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?	Y				
... use correct spelling and grammar?	Y				
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)	Y				
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)	Y				

... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy & paste text)	Y				
About the content...					
Is the deliverable content correctly written?	Y				
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?	Y				
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?	Y			The Executive Summary is just one paragraph (5 lines). Some additional useful information could be added: main features of the community platform used, activities, KPIs	
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?	Y			As a planning document (for "PLATOON Online Community") a higher level of detail should be given in terms of "what" and "when" will be done: features to be activated, spaces to be added, online events, goals for the KPIs	
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?		N		Contents of Section 4 must be reviewed and double-checked with the PLATOON website, as some of the information provided (supportive partners, ambassadors, links between web and Community platform) is not consistent in both	

				sites and could be assessed as lack of coordination	
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?		N			
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?		N			
Are all references in the document included in the references section?		N			
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)		N			
TECHNICAL RESEARCH WPs (WP2-WP5)					
Is the deliverable sufficiently innovative?					
Does the document present technical soundness and its methods are correctly explained?					
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?					
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?					
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.					
VALIDATION WP (WP6)					
Does the document present technical soundness and the validation methods are correctly explained?					
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?					
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?					
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.					
DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION WPs (WP8 & WP9)					

Does the document present a consistent outreach and exploitation strategy?					
Are the methods and means correctly explained?					
What do you think is the strongest aspect of the deliverable?					
What do you think is the weakest aspect of the deliverable?					
Please perform a brief evaluation and/or validation of the results, if applicable.					

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT
5		The Executive Summary is just one paragraph (5 lines). Some additional useful information could be added: main features of the community platform used, activities, KPIs
9-10	3.1	Some of the “Stakeholder Groups” included in the Target audience could be further justified or removed
13to 15	3.2 and 3.3	As a planning document (for “PLATOON Online Community”) a higher level of detail should be given in terms of “what” and “when” will be done: features to be activated, spaces to be added, online events, goals for the KPIs
17	4.1	Contents of Section 4.1 about supportive partners and ambassadors must be reviewed and double-checked with the PLATOON website, as the information provided is not consistent in both sites
17	4.2	As a planning document a higher level of detail could be given in terms of “what” and “when” will be done regarding online activities
18	4.3	The link between the PLATOON Community Platform and the official website should be clarified: when it will be established and how (“Join” button or others)
19	4.6	The goals of the different KPIs should be defined, so that the results achieved in each of them could be compared against the goals at the end of the project or at certain intermediate milestones: open calls, mid-project, end of year 2, . . .

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

	Document accepted; no changes required.
X	Document accepted; changes required.
	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5.

(1-Poor; 2-Fair; 3-Average; 4-Good; 5-Excellent)

Using a half point scale.

Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5
					X				

6. References

- [1] H2020 Programme, AGA – Annotated Model Grant Agreement⁵
- [2] Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants, Version 1.0 25 September 2014⁶
- [3] H2020 Programme, Guidance, Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects, EUROPEAN COMMISSION, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation, Version 1.1 07 January 2020⁷
- [4] Making the Most of Your H2020 Project, Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation, European IPR Helpdesk⁸
- [5] Graphics guide to the European emblem, Publications Office of the European Union⁹
- [6] ARTICLE 38.1 – Communication activities by beneficiaries¹⁰
- [7] European IP Helpdesk¹¹

⁵ Cf. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf#page=277

⁶ Cf. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf
<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLvpwIjZTs-Lhe0wu6uy8gr7JFfmv8EZuH>

⁷ Cf. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

⁸ Cf. https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E_0.pdf

⁹ Cf. <http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

¹⁰ Cf. https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/funding-tenders/opportunities/content/article-381-%E2%80%94-communication-activities-beneficiaries_en

¹¹ Cf. www.iprhelpdesk.eu